

In the framework of WP7 of the EJPSOIL-STEROPES project, soil samples were collected in an agricultural field close to Parma in Northern Italy according to two different sampling strategies:

- Satellite-based: soil spectra were extracted from a composite bare soil layer obtained from Sentinel-2 time series . After that the Kennard-Stone algorithm was used to select 50 spectra corresponding to 50 pixels within the test site
- Random. randomly selecting 50 points within the test site.

The organic carbon of all soil samples collected using the two sampling methods was measured by dry combustion in the laboratory (ISO 10694:1995). Results are expressed as %.

The dataset, for each sampling location, provides information about the sampling strategy, the ID number, the organic carbon content (SOC_%) and the reflectance values extracted from the S2 composite bare soil layer for each S2 band (B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B8, B11, B12).